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Electrically Conductive Lignin Reinforced Polyacrylic Acid/Hyaluronic Acid Scaffolds With PEDOT:HA Nanoparticles

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ABSTRACT

Hydrogel materials are continually developing in biomedical engineering and recently a lot of effort has gone into their engineered performance in physiological applications. Porosity is an important characteristic for tissue engineering scaffolds to allow enhanced biocompatibility and the pore size needed is dependent on the application and type of tissue for which the hydrogel is being used to regenerate. Regarding biomedical applications, the use of conducting polymers is gaining in popularity due to their promising biocompatibility and potential to stimulate cell growth and proliferation through electrical stimulation. Building on previous hydrogel development by the authors, this study focuses on developing a biocompatible hydrogel scaffold with adjustable porosity and swelling capabilities, robust mechanical properties, electrical conductivity, and high thermal stability. The objective of this work is to examine the effect of freezing temperature, cross-linker and porosity on the final characteristics of the scaffold and to then determine possible applications. The porosity, swelling degree, compression strength, biocompatibility, electrical conductivity, and thermal characteristics of the final material were analyzed and were found to be affected by the varied synthesis methods used. Overall, the synthesized scaffolds exhibit good biocompatibility with increased fluorescence over 3 days and over 70% cell viability, thermal stability up to 200°C and a range of swelling of 1725% to 8472%. They also portray robust mechanical properties with a Young's Moduli range of 11 kPa to 4.54 MPa and a porosity range of 0.78–71.98 μm depending on the synthesis methods used. Through variations in synthesis methods, highly porous, absorbent, and stable scaffolds have been synthesized. Notably, this single recipe is highly tailorable for use in a range of biomedical applications from tissue engineering to drug delivery and wound repair.

1 | Introduction

Hydrogels are 3-D polymer networks that can absorb high quantities of water and swell to many times their weight without dissolving. They have been used in numerous areas of biomedicine in applications such as contact lenses, wound

repair, tissue engineering, drug delivery, and so forth, due to their desirable characteristics including biocompatibility, hydrophilicity and capability to mimic native biological tissues [1–4]. Many of these are commercially available and patented for use in clinical settings and are produced across the world with a predicted market value of \$31.4 billion in 2027 [5, 6].

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However, some of their potential uses can be limited by their poor mechanical properties, low porosity, reduced biological interactions and inferior electrical or thermal properties. To address these shortcomings, novel hydrogel scaffolds are currently being investigated that combine natural polymers with stronger materials and incorporating nanomaterials and other fillers to enhance their properties and viability in biomedical applications [7–9]. The synthesis methods utilized to produce scaffolds also influence their mechanical, thermal, biological, and chemical characteristics, depending on the steps used. Changing the monomer or initiator concentration, reaction conditions, hydrophobic/hydrophilic ratios, or polymer/additive ratios can also have a major effect on the final attributes of the hydrogels [10, 11].

Recently, researchers have been investigating novel ways to improve a hydrogel's ability to mimic the properties of human tissues more closely to improve interactions with native cells and avoid rejection by the immune system. When it comes to biomedical applications such as tissue engineering or medical device implants, the incorporation of porosity in hydrogels is an important characteristic to more closely simulate native tissues [12]. Porous materials allow the integration of cells into the material, the dispersion of oxygen and nutrients and the outward diffusion of therapeutics [13–15]. The degree of porosity also significantly affects the mechanical, swelling and biological characteristics, with increased porosity leading to decreased stiffness in a scaffold. Thus, there must be a particular balance struck between porosity and stiffness depending on the application [16, 17]. Freeze-drying, or lyophilisation, has been used in this area to synthesize highly porous hydrogel structures [15]. Pore sizes produced by this method can be adjusted by the freezing temperature used before lyophilisation, cross-linker amount and the ratios and molecular weights of polymers used during synthesis [18, 19].

Additionally, incorporating electrical conductivity into scaffolds has many benefits when interacting with human tissues. Conductive scaffolds have been effective in tissue engineering applications to encourage physiological functions such as electrical signaling, tissue regeneration, wound healing, neurite outgrowth, and cell migration, proliferation and alignment [20–23]. The addition of conductivity in hydrogel scaffolds has many exciting benefits in cell studies and cell regulation as they can simulate bioelectric signals present in tissues such as cardiac, nerve, and neuronal. Through electrical stimulation, these scaffolds can improve cell proliferation, differentiation, and alignment, which is critical for more viable regenerative tissue scaffolds [24, 25]. There is also the possibility of real-time monitoring of cell behaviors through utilizing these electrical signals to assess cell health and differentiation in a non-invasive way [26, 27]. Another possibility is electrically controlled drug release, to regulate the delivery of bioactive molecules or growth factors to influence cell behavior over a time period [28, 29]. The addition of nanoparticles to a hydrogel can impart additional characteristics such as magnetism, stimuli-sensitivity and provide carriers for controlled release [30–32]. Polypyrrole (PPy), and polyaniline (PANI) and have frequently been used to improve the conductivity of scaffold materials. However, they have numerous drawbacks such as insolubility in water, poor biocompatibility and low conductivity

in neutral pH environments [33, 34]. Alternatively, poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) polystyrene sulfonate (PEDOT:PSS) is a commercially available conducting polymer used for tissue engineering that has improved solubility in water, but it too has its limitations as it relies on PSS as a stabilizer. PSS not only reduces its conductivity as it is an insulating component, but also has poor biocompatibility and biofunctionality, as it can release harmful acidic components upon degradation [35, 36]. To overcome this, novel PEDOT:HA nanoparticles previously synthesized by the current authors are used in this study. These nanoparticles used hyaluronic acid as a biocompatible alternative to PSS, creating highly stable, biocompatible, and electrically conductive nanoparticles [37].

Finally, material selection is a very significant in scaffold optimisation. The appropriate combination of materials allows for the favorable characteristics of each to be combined while overcoming their individual disadvantages [38]. Hyaluronic acid (HA) is a naturally occurring polymer renowned for its high biocompatibility, non-toxicity, biodegradability, and exceptional water retention properties, making it ideal for various biomedical applications [39–41]. However, like most natural hydrogels, it has poor mechanical properties and can be degraded via oxidation or enzymes which limits its practical uses. To address these challenges, HA can be blended with other natural or synthetic materials that offer improved mechanical properties. Lignin (LIG), another natural material, has attracted interest in biomedicine due to its biodegradability, biocompatibility, thermal stability and its antimicrobial and antioxidant qualities, also making it promising for hydrogel applications [42]. Until recently, it was widely considered as a waste byproduct, produced in the pulp and paper industry [43, 44]. In recent years, research on its valorisation has increased hugely. Applications of lignin include biosensors, controlled release, electrodes and as sustainable alternatives to carbon fibers [44–47]. Synthetic polymers commonly used in hydrogels, such as poly(vinyl) alcohol (PVA), polyethylene glycol (PEG), and acrylic acid derivatives offer excellent mechanical properties, low toxicity, good biocompatibility, and reproducibility but may lack adequate cell attachment capabilities. Thus, a combination of natural and synthetic polymers can overcome the limitations of both. Polyacrylic acid (PAA), for instance, is a biocompatible and biodegradable polymer that finds application alone or in combination with other materials as a biological adhesive, mucoadhesive for drug delivery systems, and surface coatings for biomedical devices [48–50]. It can produce hydrogels capable of absorbing many times their weight in water and it has been known to be a superabsorbent, making it a desirable option when developing biocompatible and bioactive hydrogels for biomedical applications [51–53]. Using hyaluronic acid, lignin, and acrylic acid, a novel hydrogel will be produced that will synergistically harness the positive characteristics and improve the limitations of each material.

As mentioned, the authors previously synthesized novel PEDOT:HA nanoparticles. Prior to this study, only work done by Wang et al. has incorporated these novel materials into a hydrogel scaffold system [54]. In this work the authors incorporated these nanoparticles into a chitosan and gelatin hydrogel matrix and found that the incorporation of the NPs improved the electric properties of the hydrogel and that the overall system was biocompatible with good cell adhesion (> 71%), good mechanical

characteristics and a very high swelling ratio of 2800%. The combination of acrylic acid, hyaluronic acid and lignosulfonate has previously been examined by Glingasorn et al. to synthesize a potential medical adhesive that possesses a swelling ratio of 130% and a compression strength of 28 kPa. However, in this study [55], no biocompatibility studies or porosity data were reported. Zhang et al. synthesized a composite hydrogel of PAA and HA for wound dressing applications and achieved tailorable mechanical properties through synthesis variations [56]. This work achieved an interconnected porosity of 52%, a swelling ratio of 122% and good cytocompatibility, despite poor cell adhesion. However, the inclusion of PEDOT:HA nanoparticles into a hyaluronic acid, polyacrylic acid and lignosulfonate hydrogel scaffold has not been previously studied. Previous work done by the authors used this novel combination to synthesize highly adhesive, conductive hydrogels that had excellent elasticity, toughness, and swelling capabilities [57]. This material was found to have promise as a medical adhesive, adhesive sensor, and bioelectrode, however due to poor cell adhesion and lack of porosity in these materials, their application in tissue engineering and drug delivery was limited. Thus, the hypothesis of this work aims further the novel combination of acrylic acid, hyaluronic acid, lignin, and conductive PEDOT:HA nanoparticles to form a highly porous scaffold, whilst observing the influence of porosity and nanoparticle addition on material properties in order to determine its potential for tissue engineering applications. The incorporation of nanoparticles is intended to add a conductive element to the hydrogels and this will be analyzed through dielectric conductivity analysis of the hydrogels. The influence of nanoparticle addition on the mechanical, swelling, and biocompatibility characteristics will also be analyzed through compression testing, swelling tests, metabolic Alamar Blue assays and LIVE/DEAD assays respectively. The addition of lignosulfonate has previously been proven to increase the mechanical characteristics and elasticity of these hydrogels [57]. Its combination with acrylic acid (AA) is proposed enhance structural integrity in the scaffolds, as well as AA incorporating high hydrophilicity to the scaffold. Finally, hyaluronic acid is utilized as it is naturally biocompatible, hydrophilic and can safely degrade within the body. Thus, this experimental study uses morphological, swelling, chemical, thermal, mechanical, conductivity, and biocompatibility analysis to test the multifunctional properties of this novel material combination in a hydrogel scaffold for general biological applications.

2 | Experimental Section

2.1 | Materials

For nanoparticle and hydrogel synthesis, Sodium Hyaluronic Acid (HA, 2MDa) was purchased from Shanghai Easier Industrial Development Co. LTD. (Shanghai, China). 3,4 Ethylenedioxythiophene (EDOT, 97%), iron(III) p-toluenesulfonate hexahydrate (FeTos), hydrochloric acid, poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) polystyrene sulfonate (PEDOT:PSS) (1.3 wt %), Acrylic Acid (Stabilized with hydroquinone), lignosulfonate, and hydrogen peroxide (30 wt %) were purchased from Analab (Ireland). Ammonium persulfate, NN'-Bis(acryloyl) cystamine (98%), and Phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Ireland).

For cell culture, Alamar Blue cell viability reagent was purchased from Invitrogen (ThermoFisher, USA). Dulbecco's modified Eagle Medium (DMEM), trypsin-EDTA 0.25%, L-glutamine, Penicillin-Streptomycin, Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS), DAPI and propidium iodine were all purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Ireland). NIH/3T3 fibroblast cell line was purchased from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC, USA).

2.2 | Synthesis of PEDOT:HA NPs

Nanoparticles were synthesized as per our previous work [37] and can be seen in Figure 2. Briefly, HA powder was dissolved in 0.1 M hydrochloric acid, followed by EDOT and then stirred for 10 mins. The obtained emulsion is placed in an ice bath under tip sonification to form a miniemulsion and then added to a flask for additional stirring. Following this, FeTos was dissolved in DI water and stirred until dissolved. This solution was added slowly to the emulsion and the mixture was left under magnetic stirring to polymerize. Hydrogen peroxide was added after 1 h, and the solution was then left to polymerize overnight. The obtained nanoparticles were purified using three runs of centrifugation, redispersing in DI water before each additional run. The nanoparticles were then dispersed in 40 mL of DI water and sonicated until fully redispersed. The nanoparticles were stored in a sealed container until hydrogel synthesis.

2.3 | Synthesis of Hydrogels

Initially, 0.1 g of Hyaluronic acid (HA) was added to a beaker containing 20 mL of DI water and the solution was stirred overnight until the HA was fully dissolved. Following this, for samples containing nanoparticles (NPs) 0.25 mL of dispersed PEDOT:HA NPs were added to the beaker and stirred and sonicated until a well-dispersed distribution was achieved. Then, 0.2 g lignosulfonate (LIG), 3.6 mL of acrylic acid (AA) and varied amounts of NN'-Bis(acryloyl)cystamine (BACA) were added to the solution, stirred and sonicated. Finally, 0.03 g of ammonium persulfate (APS) was added and stirred until a homogeneous sample was achieved. The solution was then poured into a petri dish (films) or a mold and placed in an oven for 3 h at 80°C. Controls were prepared following the same recipe but containing no NPs. The compositions of each scaffold are shown in Table A of Supporting Information and Figure 1 shows the fabrication mechanism and of the hydrogel and the cross-linking of AA, using BACA.

Following curing, the hydrogels were divided and frozen at -70°C, -20°C or using liquid nitrogen. These samples were then transferred to the freeze-dryer (Christ Alpha 2-4 LSCplus, Germany) to dry for 2 days. Prior to freeze-drying, the samples at -70°C and -20°C were frozen for three full days and the LN₂ samples were frozen just before freeze-drying. The entire preparation schematic of the hydrogels is shown in Figure 2.

2.4 | Swelling Tests

To prepare for swelling, the scaffolds were fully dried overnight in a vacuum oven at 60°C. Immediately after drying,

FIGURE 1 | (A) Fabrication of PAA/HA/LIG/PEDOT:HA hydrogels using Bis(acryloyl)cystamine (BACA) as cross-linker. (B) Chemical structure of BACA cross-linked PAA.

they were weighed to get their initial weight (W_d) and swollen in 10 mL of solvent in a sealed vial for the duration of the study. Samples were removed from the solvent, dried with filter paper to remove excess solvent and then weighed at defined intervals to get the swollen weight of the samples (W_s). The following formula was used to determine the swelling degree of the samples:

$$\frac{W_s - W_d}{W_d} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Swelling tests were completed with either DI water or PBS at either 20°C or 37°C for 48 h. Long-term studies were also completed to assess degradation profiles.

2.5 | Morphological Analysis

Visual morphological analysis of the hydrogels was conducted using SEM analysis with the Hitachi SU70 SEM at 5 kV. The hydrogels were synthesized as per above and following synthesis, they were gold sputtered and imaged. Image J (FIJI) was employed to analyze porosity in the samples.

2.6 | FTIR

A Spectrum 100 FTIR (PerkinElmer, USA) was used to obtain FTIR Spectra of the scaffolds in the range of 650–4000 cm^{-1} for 4 scans.

2.7 | Thermal Analysis

To assess the water content and thermal degradation of the samples, a Perkin Elmer TGA 4000 instrument under a nitrogen atmosphere was employed. The samples underwent gradual heating from 30°C to 800°C at a rate of 10°C/min.

For determining the glass transition temperature (T_g) using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), a Perkin Elmer DSC 6 instrument was utilized. Approximately 7 ± 1 mg of each sample was placed in an aluminum pan. Initially, the samples were heated from 50°C to 200°C at a rate of 10°C/min to eliminate any thermal history. Subsequently, they were cooled to 30°C at 20°C/min, followed by reheating to 200°C at a rate of 20°C/min. The T_g was identified from the second heating cycle.

2.8 | Mechanical Analysis

Compression testing was undertaken using an IMADA Force-Displacement Measurement unit to observe the mechanical characteristics of the hydrogels. The hydrogels were cut into circular discs with a diameter of 10 mm and a height of 2 mm. A compression speed of 1 mm/min was used, and each sample was measured in triplicate, with the mean \pm standard deviation shown. The following equations were used to determine the stress and strain values of the samples from the data obtained:

$$\text{stress} = \frac{F}{A} \quad (2)$$

FIGURE 2 | Synthesis process of hydrogel scaffolds with initial hydrogel synthesis, freezing and freeze-drying steps.

$$\text{strain} = \Delta l / l_0 \quad (3)$$

F is the force (N), A is the cross-sectional area of the sample (m), l_0 is the original height of the sample (mm) and Δl is the change of height recorded (mm).

The compressive strength was determined from the results and the Young's moduli of the samples were calculated from the slope of the initial linear region of the stress versus strain curve.

2.9 | Biological Analysis

NIH-3T3 fibroblasts were maintained in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS), 1% L-glutamine, and 1% streptomycin-penicillin solution at 37°C in a humidified environment with 5% CO₂. The culture medium was refreshed every 3 days until the cells

reached approximately 80% confluence. Before cell seeding, the scaffolds underwent thorough washing with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), sterilization under ultraviolet (UV) light for 2 h, and immersion in DMEM within a 24-well plate. The scaffolds were then incubated at 37°C for 72 h to achieve equilibrium swelling. Subsequently, cells were seeded onto these pre-treated scaffolds at a density of 50,000 cells per well in a 24-well plate, with 1 mL of cell culture medium added to each well, followed by overnight incubation.

For cytotoxicity evaluation, a 10% volume of Alamar Blue was added to each well and incubated for an initial period of 4 h. Aliquots from the samples were transferred to a 96-well plate for fluorescence measurement using a SynergyMx plate reader (BioTek, UK) at an excitation/emission wavelength of 540/590 nm. Measurements were taken at 4, 24, and 48 h post-Alamar Blue addition. Control cells were cultured in complete DMEM without scaffolds. Statistical analysis to compare groups and controls was performed using one-way ANOVA, with significance defined at $p < 0.05$.

Following the above cell culture protocol, NIH-3T3 fibroblast cells were stained with Calcein AM to mark live cells and Propidium Iodide for dead cells, enabling live/dead imaging using the ImageXpress Micro Spinning Disc Confocal High-Content Imaging System (Molecular Devices). This fluorescence microscopy technique visualized live (green) and dead (red) cells, facilitating the assessment of cell attachment and viability. Images were further processed and analyzed with Fiji ImageJ software.

2.10 | Conductivity Analysis

Dielectric measurements were conducted using a Novocontrol Broadband Dielectric Spectrometer (Hundsagen, Germany) equipped with an Alpha Analyzer, covering a frequency range from 4×10^{-2} to 4×10^6 Hz. The measurements took place under a nitrogen atmosphere at a controlled temperature of 37°C, maintained by the Novocontrol Quatro cryosystem, ensuring an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ during each frequency sweep. Disc-shaped samples, approximately 2–3 mm thick and 10 mm in diameter, were utilized, with experimental uncertainty kept below 5% in all cases. The experiments were performed on both dried and re-hydrated samples, the latter being rehydrated in deionized (DI) water. An excitation voltage of 1 V was applied during the measurements.

2.11 | Statistical Analysis

For biological analysis, experiments were completed in triplicate and the data is presented as mean \pm standard deviation. To determine statistical significance between groups, two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used, with a *p* value of < 0.05 deemed significantly significant ($*p < 0.05$).

3 | Results

3.1 | Morphology

Figure 3 shows the cross-section of lyophilised hydrogels. It was observed that the porosity varied with cross-linker amounts and with initial freezing temperature prior to freeze-drying. Generally, a slower freezing step in the synthesis process results in the formation of larger ice crystals and therefore, large pores following lyophilisation. The samples initially frozen with LN_2 show a regular porous structure with very small pore sizes due to very rapid freezing. As expected from previous literature, samples frozen at a higher temperature form larger pores due to a slower freezing rate [19]. This is the case in these samples, as the -20°C has the largest porosity as it has the slowest rate of freezing, for example the $-20_{-0.12}$ sample has a pore size of $32 \pm 7 \mu\text{m}$ compared to $26 \pm 13 \mu\text{m}$ and $3.4 \pm 0.9 \mu\text{m}$ in the $-70_{-0.12}$ and $\text{LN}_2_{-0.12}$ samples respectively. An increase in cross-linker also leads to smaller pores and a more densely cross-linked network [58]. In the case of the -70 samples the pore size decreases from $33 \pm 8 \mu\text{m}$ in the 0.08 sample to $26 \pm 12 \mu\text{m}$ in the 0.12 sample and $11 \pm 5 \mu\text{m}$ in the 0.16 sample. However, the densely cross-linked network achieved in the $\text{LN}_2_{-0.16}$ samples appear to have pores below

the resolution of the images, with an overall porosity percentage of $18\% \pm 0.6\%$. The 0.16 samples overall show a lower porosity percentage with the $-70_{-0.16}$ and $-20_{-0.16}$ samples displaying a porosity percentage of $42\% \pm 4\%$ and $32\% \pm 5\%$ respectively. This porosity influences swelling and cell integration in these materials, therefore these results imply that a cross-linker of 0.12 or 0.08 may be more suitable for scaffold applications with a porosity percentage of 46%–65% and 54%–60% in these samples respectively. It is also important to note that the samples frozen with liquid nitrogen, tended to be quite brittle and can crack upon initial freezing making it difficult to regulate the size and shape of the samples, as well as other limitations that will be discussed later in this section. Overall, Figure 3 demonstrates the tailorability of these hydrogels with regard to porosity, depending on the freezing temperature and cross-linker levels used. The porosity seen in these samples is important for good fluid absorption properties and the interconnected network is beneficial to the transmission of oxygen and nutrients. Samples with a larger pore size generally swell more, provide a higher drug-loading capacity and a faster release of therapeutics [59, 60]. It is also important to match the porosity to the constraints of the cell intended for seeding on the scaffolds and thus depending on the intended application, this recipe can be tailored to a suitable porosity, pores size and therefore cell type. Due to the very small pore sizes shown in the LN_2 samples ($< 3.4 \pm 0.9 \mu\text{m}$), these samples would be unlikely to promote cell ingrowth as the size of many commonly used cells is much higher than this. The average size of fibroblast cells is 15–20 μm , 10–30 μm for epithelial cells, neuronal cells can range from 10 to 50 μm and endothelial cells are 10–20 μm in diameter [61]. For this reason, the use of the -20 and -70 samples would be more suitable for cell growth and integration into the scaffolds, with the -70 samples showing the most promising porosity overall.

3.2 | Swelling

Swelling of the hydrogels was measured over several parameters including varied solvents, temperature and times and results are shown in Figure 4. While Figure 5 shows the swelling of the scaffolds over 48 h comparing NP samples swollen at 37°C in PBS, at 37°C in DI water, at 20°C in DI water and control (CON) samples swollen at 37°C in DI water to compare the effect of different parameters on swelling. Firstly, the effect of cross-linker content on the swelling is observed. The swelling trend in the CON samples without nanoparticles swollen in DI water shows a distinct decrease in swelling with an increase in cross-linker amount, for instance, the $-70_{-0.08_CON}$ sample has a swelling of 8150 ± 90 , reducing to 5600 ± 300 in the $-70_{-0.12_CON}$ sample and 5000 ± 400 in the $-70_{-0.16_CON}$ sample. This is due to increasing cross-linked densities implying there is less free volume to accommodate liquid and thus the swelling decreases. Interestingly, this trend is not as visible in the samples containing nanoparticles, swollen in DI water, for example in the $-70_{-0.08_NP}$ sample the swelling is 4200 ± 200 , lowering to 3040 ± 80 in the $-70_{-0.12_NP}$ sample but then rising to 4200 ± 400 in the $-70_{-0.16_NP}$ sample. This may indicate that the addition of nanoparticles not only decreases the overall swelling ratio but also may have an effect on the cross-linking efficiency when a certain threshold of nanoparticles is present.

FIGURE 3 | (A–I) SEM images of lyophilised scaffolds with varying cross-linker amounts (0.08%, 0.12%, and 0.16%) and varied freezing temperatures (LN₂, -70°C and -20°C), scale bar is varied for improved focus, (J) average pore sizes in all lyophilised samples calculated using ImageJ **p* < 0.05, (*n* = 5, mean ± SD) is indicated where statistical difference is observed within groups. (K) porosity percentage of all scaffolds calculated using ImageJ from SEM images, **p* < 0.05, (*n* = 5, mean ± SD) is indicated where statistical difference is observed within groups.

Next, the effect of freezing temperature on the swelling degree is observed. Generally, the samples frozen initially with liquid nitrogen show slightly lower swelling overall due to the presence of smaller pores compared to that of the -70°C and -20°C samples. Again, this is more prominent in the CON samples. The swelling solvent used also indicates little impact on the swelling over 2 days, but the effect is more clearly seen in long-term swelling conditions shown in Figure A of Supporting Information in which the one-month swelling graphs of samples in PBS and DI water are shown. Samples swollen in PBS stabilize after 2 days and remain stable for up to 1 month; for example, the -70_0.12_NP sample has a swelling degree of 4500 ± 800 after 2 days and stays consistent at 4600 ± 600 at

1 month. However, the DI swollen samples continue increasing in weight up to 1 month, with the -70_0.12_NP sample increasing by 30%, from a swelling degree of 3000 ± 80 to 3900 ± 100. As PBS more closely resembles bodily fluid due to the normal salt content of body fluids and tissues, this indicates that swelling may be stabilized in the body after 2 days. Swelling studies on non-freeze-dried samples tend to show less stable samples with obvious sample degradation following 2 days of exposure [57].

Finally, the influence of the temperature of swelling used was examined with samples swollen at 20°C (room temperature) showing a much lower swelling degree than samples swollen

FIGURE 4 | Swelling graphs up to 48 h of (A–C) all PAA/HA/LIG/NP samples swollen in PBS at 37°C, (D–F) PAA/HA/LIG/NP samples swollen in DI water at 20°C, (G–I) PAA/HA/LIG/NP samples swollen in DI water at 37°C, (J–L) PAA/HA/LIG/CON samples swollen in DI water at 37°C.

at 37°C (body temperature). Overall, all samples show a very high level of swelling across different temperatures and solvent environments, with the most controlled high swelling over long-term studies seen at 37°C in PBS, the conditions that most closely resemble biological. All freeze-dried samples show good stability and stay fully intact over long-term studies without any visual disintegration/degradation.

3.3 | FTIR

Chemical analysis of the hydrogels was carried out using FTIR, as depicted in Figure 6. A broad peak in the range of 3600 to 3200 cm^{-1} , shown in Figure 6a,b, indicates the presence of hydroxyl groups in AA, HA, LIG, and PEDOT. The peak at 2934 cm^{-1} corresponds to the C–H stretching vibration of the acrylate unit,

FIGURE 5 | Total swelling degree (%) over 2 days of all samples, comparing (A) PAA/HA/LIG hydrogels containing nanoparticles and swollen in DI water at 20°C, (B) PAA/HA/LIG hydrogels containing nanoparticles and swollen in PBS at 37°C, (C) PAA/HA/LIG hydrogels containing nanoparticles and swollen in DI water at 37°C and (D) PAA/HA/LIG hydrogels containing no nanoparticles (CON) and swollen in DI water at 37°C.

associated with HA [62]. Figure 6c provides a detailed view of the spectra between 900 and 1800 cm^{-1} . The characteristic peak at 1700 cm^{-1} , related to the C=O stretching of the carboxyl groups of PAA, confirms successful polymerization. The peak at 1630 cm^{-1} is attributed to HA, while the peak at 1040 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of lignin, confirming their successful incorporation into the hydrogel. Although the absorption peaks associated with the PEDOT nanoparticles are less prominent, the peak at 810 cm^{-1} , related to the stretching vibrations of the C—S—C bond in the thiophene ring of PEDOT, suggests their presence [63]. Additionally, the peak at 1455 cm^{-1} , attributed to the C—N vibration of PAA, indicates successful cross-linking of acrylic acid [64, 65]. These findings demonstrate the successful formation of a hydrogel composed of PAA/HA/LIG and PEDOT nanoparticles.

3.4 | Thermal Analysis

The effect of the composition and freezing temperature of the scaffolds on their thermal stability was assessed using

FIGURE 6 | FTIR Spectra of (A) -70_0.08_NP, -70_0.12_NP, and -70_0.16_NP hydrogel samples, (B) LN2_0.12_CON, -70_0.12_CON, and -20_0.12_CON hydrogel samples and (C) a close up of the -70_0.08_NP, -70_0.12_NP, and -70_0.16_NP hydrogel samples from 950 to 1800 cm^{-1} .

thermogravimetric analysis and differential scanning calorimetry. Figure 7a depicts the thermal decomposition of the hydrogel samples, with samples all showing a similar pattern of thermal degradation and little change in the thermograms across initial freezing temperatures. Initial stage weight loss of 4% was observed in the samples due to the evaporation of residual water still retained by the hydrogels prior to testing. This evaporation occurred up to 153°C in the LN₂ sample, 165°C in the -20 sample and 187°C in the -70 sample. Most of the weight loss in these samples occurred between 160°C and 500°C which is a result of the degradation of polymer main chains and side chains. After 500°C the sample weight plateaued, with a final weight of 11%–12% char [66]. The influence of nanoparticles on the hydrogel has been evaluated previously and it was found that the thermal stability of the material was reduced minimally [57]. Overall, the addition of nanoparticles or the difference in freezing temperatures does not have a notable effect on the thermal stability of the samples.

To eliminate the broad endothermic peak caused by moisture loss in the hydrogel, only the second differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) heat scan of the samples is shown in Figure 7b–d. The DSC analysis reveals that the glass transition temperatures of the samples ranged from 103°C to 123°C, as detailed in Table B of Supporting Information. An exception was observed in the -20_0.16_NP sample, which exhibited a glass transition temperature of 88.178°C, suggesting an impact on cross-linking in this sample. As expected for hydrogels, no melting event was detected in the second heat scan below 200°C. Notably, the glass transition temperature decreased with an increase in

the cross-linker amount during synthesis. This trend is associated with the plasticizing effect of higher water content in the samples, indicating greater water retention in those with lower cross-linking [67], as mentioned in the swelling results of this paper. The same reasoning can be related to the samples frozen using liquid nitrogen showing a higher glass transition temperature compared to the -70 and -20 samples as the latter retains higher amounts of water.

3.5 | Mechanical Analysis

Unconfined compression testing was performed on the scaffolds to analyze their mechanical characteristics. The moduli and compressive strength of the samples were obtained and are presented in Figure 8. The freeze-dried scaffolds have good strength and high moduli which can be attributed to a combination of hydrogen bonding, a covalently bonded network due to the presence of AA and disulfide cross-linking bridges present in the scaffolds [68]. With increased cross-linker, the control samples show an increase in stiffness with a Young's Modulus of 1.80 ± 0.13 MPa in the LN₂_0.08_CON sample increasing to 2.3 ± 0.2 MPa and 3.1 ± 0.6 MPa in the LN₂_0.12_CON and LN₂_0.16_CON samples respectively. The same increase is seen in the CON -70 and -20 samples. However, nanoparticle addition in all samples but the -20_0.08 scaffold, shows a decrease in the stiffness of the material. This is likely due to the nanoparticles reducing the cross-linking efficiency of the samples, leading to less stiff and less densely cross-linked samples which correlates well with swelling data. With regards to the effect

FIGURE 7 | (A) TGA graphs comparing the weight loss up to 700°C of 0.12_NP samples (B–D) DSC thermographs of all PAA/HA/LIG/PEDOT:HA samples from 50°C to 200°C.

FIGURE 8 | (A) Compressive strength of all scaffold samples (MPa), linear scale. (B) Young's Modulus of all scaffold samples with varied freezing temperatures, varied cross-linker addition and with/without nanoparticle addition (Pa), logarithmic scale.

of freezing temperature and porosity on the mechanical characteristics of the samples, the LN₂_CON samples show a much higher modulus than the -70 and -20 samples. For example, the LN₂_0.16_CON sample exhibits a modulus of 3.1 ± 0.6 MPa, whereas the -70_0.16_CON and -20_0.16_CON samples show a much lower modulus of 0.6 ± 0.13 MPa and 0.5 ± 0.3 MPa respectively. The LN₂ scaffolds have a very highly interconnected cross-linking network with very small pores that lead to a much stiffer material than the much larger pores of the -20 and -70 samples. The addition of nanoparticles also reduces the compressive strength significantly in the -70 and -20 samples with the -70_0.12 sample reducing from 4.5 ± 0.2 MPa to 1.72 ± 0.15 MPa for example. However, the addition of nanoparticles does not have a significant effect on the compressive strength of the LN₂ samples, with all showing a similar stress at failure. Overall, the -70_0.16_CON sample shows the highest compressive strength and the LN₂_0.16_CON sample exhibits the highest modulus. All samples exhibit very high mechanical characteristics and modulating the cross-linker addition, freezing temperature and addition of nanoparticles allows for this to be tailored depending on application. For example, to synthesize a biomimetic scaffold, the mechanical characteristics of the scaffold must closely resemble that of the target tissue. These samples have a Young's Moduli range of 11 kPa to 4.54 MPa, depending on synthesis methods, meaning that they have the potential for a range of applications requiring different mechanical characteristics.

3.6 | Biocompatibility Testing

To assess the potential cytotoxicity of the scaffolds, an Alamar Blue proliferation assay was utilized. NIH-3T3 fibroblast cells were cultured on the scaffolds, and their fluorescence was measured to monitor cell proliferation over a 48-h period. This data was then compared to a control group where cells were cultured directly on a well plate without scaffolds. The fluorescence results, depicted in Figure 9, show the proliferation of the cells over 3 days. All samples show increased fluorescence over 3 days which indicates that these hydrogels have good biocompatibility over time. This is important for samples that are intended for use in vivo as the cells continue to proliferate in their presence over 3 days. The samples frozen with liquid nitrogen show the lowest proliferation

across the freeze-dried samples and this is possibly due to the presence of very small pores. With a general average diameter of $18 \mu\text{m}$ for NIH-3T3 cells, the very small porosity of around $0.78\text{--}3.36 \mu\text{m}$ measured in the liquid nitrogen samples would likely be too small to promote cell ingrowth, thus the cells would only proliferate on the surface of these hydrogels and thus have a lower overall fluorescence than the -70 and -20 freeze-dried samples. The -70 samples however have a pore diameter of around $26\text{--}95 \mu\text{m}$ and the -20 samples have a pore diameter of $15\text{--}32 \mu\text{m}$ which should allow the cells to settle and proliferate within the porosity network, giving the cells more surface area to grow. In this case, the control has a lower fluorescence generally than the -70 and -20 samples, which may be due to a smaller surface area for the inherently adherent cells to proliferate compared to the highly porous samples. The addition of nanoparticles shows a decrease in fluorescence in the LN₂ samples and despite improving the fluorescence in the -70_0.12 and -20_0.12 samples, it does not have a significant effect on fluorescence in the -70 or -20 samples over all samples tested. One-way ANOVA shows a statistical increase in proliferation of each group over the 3 days. Any other statistical difference between the groups is shown in the Figure 9.

LIVE/DEAD staining was used to visualize NIH-3T3 cells cultured on the scaffolds over 2 days, with live cells shown in green and dead cells shown in red. Cell viability was calculated using Image J to process the images and cell viability was above 70% in all samples which indicates high cell viability. Despite this, the cells seen in Figure 9e are very spherical and poor cell adhesion is indicated by the lack of characteristic spindle-like morphology that is typical of fibroblast cells. This is likely due to a lack of adhesion sites present in AA, preventing the cells from adhering to the sample surface. Despite poor adhesion, the cells do exhibit good cell viability, with the -70 samples showing the highest overall live cells with all samples above $82\% \pm 2\%$ viability. Both -20 samples and LN₂ samples all show a high ratio of live cells also with scaffolds showing over $73\% \pm 3\%$ and $70\% \pm 5\%$ viability respectively. The addition of nanoparticles to the scaffolds does not have a significant effect on the cell viability across the samples with some trends increasing and some decreasing, indicating that the addition of NPs does not elicit a cytotoxic effect on these scaffolds. Compared to previous work done on these materials [57], the incorporation of porosity in these scaffolds

FIGURE 9 | (A–C): 3-day fluorescence (% reduction of alamarBlue reagent) of all samples, * $p < 0.05$, $n = 3$, mean \pm SD) is indicated where a statistical difference is observed, (D) LIVE/DEAD assay-based cell viability quantification, analyzed from images in (E) using ImageJ. (E) LIVE/DEAD staining of NIH-3T3 cells seeded onto all scaffolds for a period of 48 h.

increases the number of cells present at the time of imaging, implying that the incorporation of porosity into the scaffolds has improved the limitations observed previously in the experimental setup in which cells get washed away during washing steps. Additional larger images of LIVE/DEAD imaging can be found in Figure B of Supporting Information.

3.7 | Conductivity Analysis

In order to determine the conductivity of the hydrogels, dielectric analysis was employed. Figure 10a–c shows the frequency

dependence of the dielectric permittivity and conductivity of all samples. The dielectric permittivity of all samples decreases with increasing frequency whereas the conductivity increases with increasing frequency. Figure 10d–f show the AC conductivity and dielectric permittivity of samples at 1 Hz at 37°C. Hydrated samples were used as the goal of most scaffolds for tissue engineering is to be implanted in vivo, with body fluids causing the samples to hydrate and swell. Dry samples were previously studied and were found to have considerably lower conductivity than wet samples [57]. This is due to the ionic contributions from the water working with the addition of nanoparticles to increase conductivity and improve the interaction between electroconductive materials

FIGURE 10 | (A–C) Frequency dependence of the dielectric permittivity (ϵ') and conductivity (σ_{ac}) at 37°C in samples frozen at –20°C, –70°C, and LN₂ respectively. (D–F) Conductivity and dielectric permittivity at 37°C at 1 Hz of hydrated AA/HA/LIG samples initially frozen at –20°C, –70°C, and LN₂ respectively.

and biological tissue [69]. Conductivity in the NP-laden scaffolds ranged from 7.336×10^{-5} S/cm in the $-70_{-0.16_NP}$ sample to 6.3×10^{-3} S/cm in the $LN2_{0.08_NP}$ sample. This is comparable to other studies incorporating a higher percentage of PEDOT:HA nanoparticles into a hydrogel scaffold or film material [54, 70].

4 | Conclusions

The current synthesis methods produce highly porous and stable hydrogels with good mechanical properties, a very high swelling degree, biocompatibility and conductivity. The varied synthesis methods used were found to have a significant effect on the porosity, swelling degree, mechanical, biological, and thermal characteristics of the final material. The hydrogels produced in this study demonstrate several critical characteristics that make them clinically significant in applications such as biomedical devices and tissue engineering. With a cell viability of over 70%, it indicates that these hydrogels will be well tolerated by biological tissues and reduces the likelihood of adverse immune responses. Their stable mechanical properties, high porosity and significant swelling capacity are appropriate for tissue engineering applications in which material characteristics and the absorption of bodily fluids can influence cell growth and tissue regeneration. Nanoparticle addition to these scaffolds imbued the materials with conductive characteristics, regulated the swelling and reduced mechanical properties, however, they had no significant effect on biological and thermal results. Nanoparticle addition allows tuning of properties, which could be beneficial in applications such as tissue scaffolds and nerve regeneration. In this study, only one variation in nanoparticle addition is analyzed (1% w/v) to observe the general influence of PEDOT:HA nanoparticles on the characteristics of a freeze-dried AA/HA/LIG hydrogel and future work will focus on the optimization of nanoparticle addition for conductivity while retaining suitable cross-linking possibly by gradients of NP concentrations. The samples frozen using liquid nitrogen had a very small porosity ($< 3.36 \pm 0.89 \mu\text{m}$) and regular crosslinking network, that endowed the hydrogel with very high mechanical characteristics but reduced their swelling degree and biocompatibility. These samples were also quite brittle during synthesis, and they were liable to thermal shock caused by the extreme sudden temperature change, making them unsuitable for use due to poor reproducibility. The samples frozen at -20°C and -70°C show the best swelling and biocompatibility, as well as having high mechanical properties and stability. These properties are crucial for wound healing applications for example, where the ability to adapt to the wound environment could improve healing. Overall, these samples portray good biocompatibility with above 70% cell viability and increased fluorescence over 3 days, a very high swelling degree, thermal stability up to 200°C and excellent mechanical properties. The materials are very tailorable with a Young's Moduli range of 11 kPa to 4.54 MPa, a porosity range of $0.78\text{--}71.98 \mu\text{m}$ and a 2-day swelling degree range of $1725\text{--}8472\%$, depending on the synthesis recipe used. Significantly, this single novel scaffold is highly tailorable, giving it the potential for use in varied applications such as adhesive sensors, skin grafts, tissue engineering, and drug delivery. The possibility to alter their properties based on synthesis methods makes these materials promising

candidates for future clinical application, as better integration with native tissues may improve patient outcomes.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy or ethical restrictions.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.